

Unveiling the link between Spiritual Intelligence and General Well-being : A Statistical Approach

Neeta Kaushik¹ and Nidhi Gulia²

1. Professor, Department of Teacher Education, J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur
2. M.Ed. Student, J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between spiritual intelligence and general well-being among higher education students in Muzaffarnagar district, Uttar Pradesh. Spiritual intelligence, encompassing dimensions such as Inner Self, Interself, Biostoria, Life Perspectives, Spiritual Actualization, and Value Orientation, plays a critical role in fostering meaning, ethical living, and emotional balance. Using a descriptive survey method, data were collected from 125 students through standardized tools: the Roqan Spiritual Intelligence Test and the PGI General Wellbeing Measure. Statistical analysis revealed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.728$, $p < 0.01$) between spiritual intelligence and general well-being. Regression analysis confirmed spiritual intelligence as a significant predictor, accounting for 53% of the variance in well-being ($R^2 = 0.530$). These findings highlight the potential of spiritual intelligence in enhancing psychological health, resilience, and life satisfaction among youth. The study underscores the need to integrate spiritual development into educational practices to promote holistic well-being.

Keywords: Spirituality, Intelligence, General Well-being.

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving world, spiritual intelligence plays a critical role in helping individuals find meaning, inner peace, and resilience amidst the challenges and complexities of modern life. As society becomes more technologically advanced and interconnected, people are facing increasing levels of stress, isolation, and disconnection from deeper sources of fulfillment. The relentless pursuit of material success, wealth, and external validation has left many feeling empty, anxious, and overwhelmed. In this context, spiritual intelligence offers a path toward inner wisdom and emotional balance by fostering a deeper understanding of life's purpose, interconnectedness, and ethical principles.

Danah Zohar was the first psychicist who coined the term "Spiritual Intelligence". In the book 'Rewiring the Corporate Brain' in 1997 by Danah Zohar, the concept of spiritual intelligence was introduced. The concept of spiritual intelligence was also suggested by Ken O' Donnel (an Australian author and consultant) in his book Endo- quality- the emotional and spiritual aspects of the living person in associations. Howard Gardner who gave the theory of multiple intelligence and because of the challenges of codifying quantifiable scientific criteria he did not include spiritual intelligence among his 'eight intelligences'. But he suggested 'existential intelligence'. Gardner's peers replied with research that project existential thinking as indispensable to spirituality.

Marshal, Zohar (2000) described spiritual intelligence to be the capacity to convey and solve the issues of value and meaning, it enables us to position our actions and lives within a broad, valuable, and meaningful context. He also added that it is the intelligence through which we can determine one action plan or direction of life is more relevant than the other. Levin (2000) explained that when we exist in a way that incorporates spiritualism into our everyday lives, spiritual intelligence is revealed. Levi posits that recognizing our interconnectedness with life as a whole, along with the ability to harness intuitive

faculties beyond the five senses, is essential for the cultivation of spirituality. This involves a deeper level of consciousness and intellect that transcends mere inquisitive and rational thought. Khavari (2000) explained that spiritual intelligence is fundamental for the attainment of our maximum human capability. It liberates ourselves from the constraints of the apparent, the content, and the immediate. Wolman (2001) has described spiritual intelligence as the capability of humans to investigate about ideal questions regarding life, and to feel at the same time the precise relationship among each of us and the universe we exist in.

Different dimensions of Spiritual Intelligence

Spiritual Intelligence is classified into the following dimensions according to Zohar and Marshall (1999).

1. Inner Self - It consists of the personal interior sense of "completeness" that is derived from continuous uprightness of character and honesty.
2. Interself - Relating with others and awareness of how one influences others. Having a helpful nature for other people with little or no interest in being rewarded for his/her efforts.
3. Biostoria - This dimension is related to the story or life experiences of one's life.
4. Life Perspectives - This dimension demonstrates affection and belief in life and also tells about sacred living.
5. Spiritual Actualization - It is the capability to identify transcendent dimensions of other's self, and of the physical world during conscious normal states.
6. Value Orientation - The foundation of value orientations is the assumption that people pursue distinct goals when making decisions that have an impact on others. A social entity or an individual's acceptance of the principles of right and wrong.

In today's society, well-being is a topic of great importance. The concept of well-being has developed with the passage of time. Well-being is a wider concept. Well-being can be defined as the balanced working of the physical and mental aspects of the personality, providing satisfaction for oneself and benefit for the society. Well-being refers to the internal or personal sense of joy, a person's place in the world of work, feeling of attainment, usefulness, attachment, contentment with experiences of life and absence of distress, dissatisfaction or worry. The well-being of a student is contingent upon the growth and integration of five areas into a harmonious whole: physical, mental, emotional, social, and spiritual. It is crucial to improve the well-being of young people, as they must surmount significant challenges to achieve success in their education, despite their low levels of health and wellbeing (Marshall, 2004). Consequently, they must be in a state of well-being (Marshall, 2004). McGregor (2007) described that well-being means how a person think about what he can do and what he has. It can be perceived as the interchange of the resources which a person has the ability to mandate, with the help of these resources what he is capable to achieve, and what aims and needs he is able to meet in particular. Kloep et al. (2009) (Kloep, Hendry, and Saunders, 2009) explained that a person who has the capacity to face the peculiar psychological, physical and social problems means that he has the physical, psychological and social resources which are required for his complete wellness. Kazdin (2011) (Kazdin and Blase, 2011) described that another name for well-being is wellness. The idea of wellness includes the aspects of beliefs and sentiments, attitudes and behaviors. These aspects can increase a subjective sense of well-being and can have impact upon the individual's awareness of self-care.

Literature Review

Research has shown that a variety of factors, including events of life, processes of psychology, and diseases, can affect one's well being. Additionally, research has demonstrated a positive correlation between well-being and spiritual intelligence.

In addition, research conducted over a variety of different cultural landscapes and contexts has also indicated a positive correlation between spiritual intelligence and general well-being. Abdollahi (2019) discovered that students at Iranian universities who exhibit a high level of spiritual intelligence reported a higher level of general well-being in different areas of environmental mastery, self-

development, and purpose of life. Karimzadeh(2021) reported that students of Malaysian university with elevated spiritual intelligence demonstrated enhanced well-being, reduced anxiety, and reduced depression.. In addition, people with better psychological well-being posit a better immune system and are well equipped to handle stress and other problems . Thus, it is necessary to focus on mental well-being to stop wrong clinical outcomes and maintain a proper immune system .

Prior research indicates that spiritual intelligence facilitates the development of self-transcendence, characterized by a transition from egocentrism to a more expansive, interconnected viewpoint (Nasiri, 2019). This transition will help students alleviate isolated feelings of loneliness, resulting in an improved sense of meaning and purpose in life. Furthermore, spiritual intelligence is shown for improving positive managing mechanisms, including awareness that can decrease perturbation and enhance emotional synchronization (Moeini et al., 2019).

The correlation between spiritual intelligence and psychological well-being was discovered in a study conducted by Ahoei et al. (2017). Students who possess a high level of spiritual intelligence are capable of effectively adapting to their surroundings. Spiritual intelligence is believed to be a significant factor in the promotion of positive psychological well-being, according to researchers. This is in accordance with , who asserted that Spiritual intelligence constitutes a psychological and religious foundation that has the potential to mitigate mental health issues and improve positive mental health. This may stem from the notion that spiritual intelligence fosters life objectives and cultivates beneficial character characteristics throughout crises, owing to one's faith in God .At times, psychological well-being may be augmented by spiritual intelligence. It is necessary for individuals to overcome their responsibilities in different life areas, particularly in the promotion of mental health and quality of life . According to a research , individuals that possess alleviated spiritual intelligence experience more happiness among their lives. This might be due to the fact that persons with a high spiritual intelligence tend to have a greater faith and perceive the world and its issues in a different and unique manner. This may significantly affect individuals' physical and mental well-being, reduce negative feelings such as anxiety and sadness, and enhance good emotions. Spiritual intelligence can also enhance self-awareness and flexibility, thereby fostering a greater capacity to tolerate the challenges and adversities of life. In other words, resilience may be enhanced by spiritual intelligence, as demonstrated by Khosravi and Nikmanesh in 2014. Spiritual intelligence results in a pure mind, that might contribute to an allevated moral action or involvement in one's spiritual activities (Ronel, 2008).

Thus, the present study is aimed at filling the existent vent in the above area of research in community. Thus, it is important to understand the noteworthiness of spiritual intelligence towards general well-being. Also, not much research has been conducted on various dimensions of spiritual intelligence and their relation to general well-being which the researcher intends to do via this study.

Method and Materials

Research Design

Descriptive Survey Research Method is used for the study. This research method is the most important and widely used research method in education. It demands certain sample and tools of research for the successful operation of the study. The focus of the study is on two variables: spiritual intelligence and general well-being.

Population and Sample

Population of the present study is comprises of all students of higher education in Muzaffarnagar district. The study is conducted on 120 higher education students regardless of stream and gender from two higher education institutes (colleges) of Muzaffarnagar district of U.P.. The selection of colleges is done via lottery system i.e random sampling technique is used for collecting the sample for present study.

Tools

Following tools are used to collect data:

Roqan Spiritual Intelligence Test (RSIT) by Prof. Roquiya Zainuddin and Ms. Anjum Ahmed(2012) and PGI General Wellbeing Measure (PGIGWBM-vv) by Dr. S.K. Verma and Ms. Amita Verma(2012).

The dimensions of Spiritual Intelligence, as proposed by Zohar and Marshall (1999), encompass six key aspects: the Inner Self, the Interself, Biostoria, Life Perspectives, Spiritual Actualization, and Value Orientation. These dimensions highlight personal integrity, ethical responsibility, life experiences, existential meaning, creativity, and moral values. To assess Spiritual Intelligence, a Likert-scale questionnaire was developed and tested for reliability and validity. Reliability was determined using Cronbach’s alpha (0.73) and the Guttman Split-Half coefficient (0.70), confirming internal consistency. Validity was established through face validity, item analysis, and concurrent validity by correlating the scale with Wuthnow’s Test of Peak Experiences ($r = 0.61$, significant at 0.05 level). The reliability index (0.85) further affirmed strong validity. The normal distribution of responses indicated that 67 % of cases fell within ± 1 standard deviation, and 95.6 % within ± 2 . The study underscores the robustness of the scale in measuring Spiritual Intelligence effectively.

Moudgil et al. (1986) have made the Hindi version of the PGIGWBM-vv scale available, and they have demonstrated that the two versions produce scores that are nearly identical. The PGIGWBM-vv scale is written in English (Means of 14.2 and 14.6 for English and Hindi versions with SDs of 4.86 and 4.73 respectively). The t-value was an insignificant 0.32 only on a sample of 50 subjects, 25 of them males (25 females), 20 belonging to scheduled caste, 30 to non-scheduled castes. The correlation between the two versions was .97 ($p < .01$) (Moudgil et al. 1986).

The data was collected using google form that consisted of questions of both the questionnaires of spiritual intelligence and general well-being.

Statistical Techniques

The data are analyzed by descriptive statistical tests and inferential statistical test namely, Karl Pearson correlation coefficient and regression analysis through SPSS software(version 30).

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Statistics for Spiritual Intelligence and General Well-Being

	Spiritual Intelligence	General Well-Being
Number of students (N)	125	125
Minimum Score	240	7
Maximum Score	390	20
Mean Score	321.60	13.48
Standard Deviation	34.79	2.71
Skewness	0.63	0.88
Kurtosis	-1.30	-1.24

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics for Spiritual Intelligence (SI) and General Well-Being (GWB) among 125 students, providing insights into their distribution, central tendency, and variability. The SI scores range from 240 to 390, with a mean of 321.60, indicating a moderate to high level of spiritual intelligence among students. In contrast, GWB scores range from 7 to 20, with a mean of 13.48, suggesting that students generally experience moderate well-being. The standard deviation for SI (34.79) is considerably higher than that of GWB (2.71), indicating greater variability in spiritual intelligence compared to well-being, which is more closely clustered around the mean. Both SI and GWB exhibit positive skewness (0.63 and 0.88, respectively), meaning that more students have scores slightly below the mean, with fewer achieving very high scores. Additionally, both distributions are platykurtic, as indicated by their negative kurtosis values (-1.30 for SI and -1.24 for GWB), suggesting that scores are more widely spread out rather than concentrated around the mean.

Correlation Analysis

Relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and General Well-being

Variables	N	Correlation coefficient (r)	p
SI and GWB	125	0.728**	0.001
The Inner Self and GWB	125	0.654**	0.001
The Inter Self and GWB	125	0.693**	0.001
The Biostoria and GWB	125	0.653**	0.001
The Life Perspectives and GWB	125	0.169*	0.060
The Spiritual Actualization and GWB	125	0.664**	0.001
The Value Orientation and GWB	125	0.631**	0.001

**Significant relationship at 0.01 level (two-tailed).

*Significant relation at 0.05 level (two-tailed).

The results in table 2 indicate a **sturdy positive correlation** between *Spiritual Intelligence (SI)* and *General Well-being (GWB)* ($r = 0.728, p = 0.001$), suggesting that individuals who possess higher levels of spiritual intelligence tend to experience a higher level of well-being. Within the facets of spiritual intelligence, the **Inter Self dimension** ($r = 0.693, p = 0.001$) and the **Spiritual Actualization dimension** ($r = 0.664, p = 0.001$) showed particularly strong correlations with GWB, indicating that an individual's ability to connect with others at a deeper level and strive for spiritual growth may significantly contribute to their overall well-being. Similarly, the **Inner Self dimension** ($r = 0.654, p = 0.001$) and **Biostoria dimension** ($r = 0.653, p = 0.001$) also demonstrated substantial positive relationships with well-being, highlighting the role of self-awareness and personal life narratives in enhancing one's psychological health. The **Value Orientation dimension** ($r = 0.631, p = 0.001$) also showed a strong positive correlation, emphasizing the importance of holding meaningful personal values in shaping well-being.

Moreover, the **Life Perspectives dimension** ($r = 0.169, p = 0.060$) showed only a weak and statistically non-significant correlation with GWB, suggesting that an individual's broader outlook on life, while potentially important, may not have as strong an impact on well-being as other dimensions of spiritual intelligence.

Regression Analysis

Regression Analysis Results

	Spiritual Intelligence
Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	0.057
Standard Error	0.005
Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	0.728
t-value	11.767
Significance (p-value)	0.001

The R^2 value of 0.530 indicates that 53.0% of the variance in GWB is accounted for by SI, underscoring its substantial predictive capability. The improved R^2 (0.526) and standard error (1.86887) further validate the model's robustness. Table 3 presents the regression analysis, which investigates the influence of **Spiritual Intelligence (SI)** on **General Well-being (GWB)**. The findings demonstrate that Spiritual Intelligence is a substantial predictor of General Well-being.

Using the unstandardized coefficients, the regression equation can be expressed as:

$$GWB = -4.767 + 0.057(SI)$$

This equation indicates that for each one-unit rise in Spiritual Intelligence, General Well-being increases by 0.057 units, assuming all other variables remain constant. Moreover, the elevated standardized coefficient () signifies a robust positive correlation between SI and GWB. The t -value of 11.767 and a

significance level of indicate that this association is extremely statistically significant. The negative constant (-4.767) suggests that at extremely low levels of SI, well-being may also be low, though this should be interpreted cautiously. These findings support the idea that enhancing **Spiritual Intelligence** could lead to a significant improvement in **General Well-being**.

ANOVA Results for Regression Model

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	483.633	1	483.633	138.471	<0.001
Residual	429.599	123	3.493	-	-
Total	913.232	124	-	-	-

Note: Dependent Variable: Level of General Well-being. Predictors: (Constant), Level of Spiritual Intelligence.

Table 4 evaluates the overall significance of the regression model, determining whether Spiritual Intelligence (SI) significantly predicts General Well-being (GWB). The regression sum of squares (SS = 483.633, df = 1) represents the variation in General Well-being (GWB) explained by Spiritual Intelligence (SI), while the residual sum of squares (SS = 429.599, df = 123) accounts for unexplained variation due to other factors. The total sum of squares (SS = 913.232, df = 124) represents the overall variability in GWB. The mean square for regression (MS = 483.633) is obtained by dividing SS by its degrees of freedom (df = 1), and the mean square for residuals (MS = 3.493) is derived similarly. The F-statistic (F = 138.471), calculated as MS divided by MS, assesses the overall significance of the model. The exceedingly low p-value (<0.001) signifies that the model is extremely significant, indicating that Spiritual Intelligence substantially contributes to elucidating the variance in General Well-being. The findings indicate that the regression model is statistically significant, with Spiritual Intelligence serving as a robust predictor of General Well-being. The elevated F-value and significant p-value indicate that the independent variable (SI) accounts for a considerable percentage of the variance in GWB, underscoring the significance of SI in enhancing well-being.

Regression line for SI and GWB

Discussion and conclusion

This study provides strong empirical support for the positive association between Spiritual Intelligence and General Well-being. The results demonstrate that individuals with higher SI tend to experience greater well-being, particularly when they cultivate self-awareness, meaningful relationships, and

value-driven living. While most dimensions of SI showed strong correlations with GWB, the Life Perspectives dimension exhibited a weaker relationship, suggesting the need for further investigation into its role in well-being.

Overall, the findings underscore the importance of integrating spiritual intelligence into psychological and educational frameworks to enhance well-being. Future research should consider longitudinal studies to explore the long-term effects of SI on well-being and examine potential mediating factors such as cultural influences, personality traits, and coping strategies. By deepening our understanding of spiritual intelligence, we can develop more holistic approaches to mental health and personal growth, ultimately fostering a more fulfilling and meaningful life.

The study's findings have important implications for psychological and personal development interventions. Integrating spiritual intelligence training into counseling programs, educational settings, and workplace environments could enhance well-being by promoting self-reflection, emotional resilience, and a sense of purpose. Additionally, fostering spiritual intelligence may be particularly beneficial in mental health interventions, helping individuals cope with stress, anxiety, and existential concerns more effectively.

Suggestions

While this study establishes a strong relationship between Spiritual Intelligence (SI) and General Well-being (GWB), further research is needed to explore additional dimensions and underlying mechanisms of this relationship. One key area for future studies is conducting longitudinal research to examine how SI influences well-being over time. A long-term approach could provide insights into whether the effects of SI are consistent or fluctuate due to life experiences, stress, or personal growth.

Another important avenue is exploring mediating and moderating factors in the SI-GWB relationship. Variables such as emotional intelligence, resilience, mindfulness, and personality traits may play a role in strengthening or weakening this connection. Identifying these mediators could help develop more targeted interventions for enhancing well-being through SI. Additionally, cultural and religious influences should be investigated, as spirituality and well-being may vary based on cultural backgrounds, belief systems, and societal norms. Comparative studies across different cultures could help determine whether SI has a universal impact on well-being or if its effects are context-dependent. Further research could also examine the causal relationship between SI and GWB. Since this study only identifies correlations, experimental or intervention-based studies could test whether improving SI leads to measurable improvements in well-being. Such studies could include SI training programs in educational, clinical, and organizational settings to assess their effectiveness in enhancing psychological health.

Finally, more attention should be given to the Life Perspectives dimension, which showed a weaker correlation with well-being. Future studies could explore whether this dimension contributes to well-being in indirect ways or over longer periods. Overall, expanding research in these areas will provide a deeper understanding of how Spiritual Intelligence can be leveraged to improve mental health and life satisfaction.

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